

be most efficient (while K^+ the least efficient) in enforcing order through longrange interactions, in, for instance, the outer B and C layers of the Frank and Wen's flickering cluster structural model¹⁰ proposed for electrolyte solutions, and thereby narrowing down the 'entropy gain' of dispersed water within the clay chamber, vis-a-vis bulk water. This should lead to an 'inverse' order of the magnitude of $\hat{Q}_w$ values, i.e. $(\hat{Q}_w)_{K-Ka} > (\hat{Q}_w)_{Ca-Ka} > (\hat{Q}_w)_{Mo-Ka}$ (Ka $\equiv$ Kaolinite matrix), as observed experimentally. Such a trend is also reflected in the $\hat{C}_w$ values, the rise in $\hat{Q}_w$ with temperature being maximum for K-kaolinite clay due to a greater thermal increase in kinetic energy of the clay-bound water in the former as compared to the other two clays.

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Kinetics of Nucleophilic Substitution Reaction of 1-Chloro-2,4-dinitrobenzene with Substituted-anilines

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KINETIC behaviour of 1-chloro-2,4-dinitrobenzene towards amines has been the subject of several publications¹⁻³ in the past. Volumetry, potentiometry and spectrophotometry are some of the techniques adopted to follow the kinetics. Conductometry remained a rarely used technique². The present study aims at investigating the kinetics

of the title reaction in a aqueous dioxane medium by conductometric technique.

Experimental

1-Chloro-2,4-dinitrobenzene (B.D.H.) was purified by repeated crystallisation from absolute alcohol and dried under reduced pressure before use (m.p. 50 - 1°). The anilines (1 - 7) used (B.D.H.) were purified either by vacuum distillation (liquids) or by crystallisation (solids). Dioxane (AnalaR) was purified following literature procedure⁴.

- 1; X = H
- 2; X = Cl
- 3; X = Br
- 4; X = CH₃

- 5; X = Cl
- 6; X = OH
- 7; X = CH₃

Kinetic measurement : The reaction was followed conductometrically in a bottle type conductivity cell specially designed for this work. Separate solutions of aniline and 1-chloro-2,4-dinitrobenzene (prepared in 80% aqueous dioxane) were equilibrated at 45 ± 0.05° for 30 min. Equal volume (2 ml) of the above two solutions were mixed in the conductance cell and the rate was followed by measuring the conductance of the solution at regular intervals using a PICO (wire type) conductivity bridge. The rates were followed at least upto 60% reaction. The runs were repeated at 55 and 65°. In order to trap the HCl formed during the reaction, the concentration of the amine was always maintained at exactly twice the concentration of 1-chloro-2,4-dinitrobenzene.

All the reactions investigated gave the final substitution products (diphenylamines) in quantitative yield. The products were purified by repeated crystallisation from dioxane-alcohol solvent mixture. Identification was made possible through ir and ¹H nmr spectral data (Table 1).

Results and Discussion

Under the conditions employed in the present investigation, the reaction followed a second order kinetics, first order each in nucleophile (aniline) and substrate. The second order rate constants obtained for the various anilines at three different temperatures are reported in Table 2. Table 2 also records the activation parameters calculated following Eyring's equation,

$$\log (k_a/T) = \log (k_B/h) + \frac{\Delta S^\ddagger}{2.303R} - \frac{\Delta H^\ddagger}{2.303R} (1/T)$$

The negative value obtained for the entropy of activation suggests a transition state more organised (less entropic) than the reactants.

TABLE 1—¹H NMR CHEMICAL SHIFTS (δ) OF 2,4-DINITRODIPHENYLAMINES*

Compd no.	H(3)	H(5)	H(6)	NH	Other
1	9.18 (d, <i>J</i> 3 Hz)	8.17 (dd, <i>J</i> 10, 3 Hz)	7.16 (d, <i>J</i> 10 Hz)	9.98 (bs)	7.27–7.53 (5H, m H(2')-H(6'))
2	9.18 (d, <i>J</i> 3 Hz)	8.20 (dd, <i>J</i> 10, 3 Hz)	7.12 (d, <i>J</i> 10 Hz)	9.89 (bs)	7.49 (2H, d, <i>J</i> 8 Hz, H(2') and H(6')), 7.25 (2H, d, <i>J</i> 8 Hz, H(3') and H(5'))
3	9.18 (d, <i>J</i> 3 Hz)	8.20 (dd, <i>J</i> 10, 3 Hz)	7.14 (d, <i>J</i> 10 Hz)	9.87 (bs)	7.63 (2H, d, <i>J</i> 9 Hz, H(2') and H(6')), 7.19 (2H, d, <i>J</i> 9 Hz H(3') and H(5'))
4	9.18 (d, <i>J</i> 3 Hz)	8.15 (dd, <i>J</i> 10, 3 Hz)	7.11 (d, <i>J</i> 10 Hz)	9.93 (bs)	7.31 (2H, d, <i>J</i> 9 Hz, H(2') and H(6')), 7.17 (2H, d, <i>J</i> 9 Hz, H(3') and H(5')), 2.42 (3H, s, CH ₃)
5	9.07 (d, <i>J</i> 3 Hz)	8.44 (dd, <i>J</i> 10, 3 Hz)		9.97 (bs)	7.88 (1H, s, H(2')), 7.81 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 10 Hz, H(6')), 7.0–7.5 (5H, m, H(6), H(4') and H(5'))
6	9.01 (d, <i>J</i> 3 Hz)	8.12 (dd, <i>J</i> 10, 3 Hz)		9.97 (bs)	7.0–7.5 (5H, m, H(6), H(2') and H(4')–H(6')), 2.42 (3H, s, CH ₃)
7	8.94 (d, <i>J</i> 3 Hz)	8.16 (dd, <i>J</i> 10, 3 Hz)		9.98 (bs)	7.23 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 3 Hz, H(2')), 7.15 (1H, dd, <i>J</i> 10, 3 Hz, H(6')), 6.58–6.85 (3H, m, H(6), H(4') and H(5')), 9.63 (1H, bs, OH)

*Downfield from TMS.

TABLE 2—SECOND ORDER RATE CONSTANTS AND ACTIVATION PARAMETERS FOR THE REACTION BETWEEN ANILINES AND 1 CHLORO-2,4-DINITROBENZENE

[Substrate] = 0.2 M, [Nucleophile] = 0.4 M, Solvent : 80% aqueous dioxane (v/v)

Compd. no.	$k_2 (\times 10^4 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1})$			$\Delta H^\ddagger$	$\Delta S^\ddagger$
	318 K	328 K	338 K	K J mol ⁻¹	J K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
1	1.55	3.26	4.46	44.71	-217.8
2	0.61	1.31	2.37	57.96	-143.7
3	0.62	1.59	2.48	59.31	-137.8
4	3.90	8.07	15.34	58.52	-126.6
5	0.99	2.16	2.95	46.42	-217.83
6	2.26	4.86	6.06	41.72	-211.73
7	3.15	5.48	8.06	39.38	-206.62

Hammett plots of $\log(k/k_0)$ against the substituent constant σ gave -4.03 , -3.64 and -4.4 as the values for the reaction constant ρ at 318, 328 and 338 K respectively. The large magnitude and negative sign for ρ suggest the formation of a transition state with substantial amount of positive charge at the reaction centre.

Structure and reactivity: At each of the three temperatures investigated, the reactivity of the anilines followed the order, $p\text{-CH}_3 > m\text{-CH}_3 > m\text{-OH} > \text{simple} > m\text{-Cl} > p\text{-Br} > p\text{-Cl}$. Considering that the presence of electron-releasing substituents will facilitate the reaction, this is the order that one would anticipate. Interestingly, as expected, the σ constants for the substituents follow the reverse order.

Mechanism and rate law: The observed second order kinetics, order of reactivity of the anilines and

negative values for $\Delta S^\ddagger$ and ρ are all in conformity with the mechanism outlined in Scheme 1

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compounds were assigned on the basis of elemental analysis, ir, pmr and mass spectral data.

Scheme 2. Reagents: (i) CS_2 , liq. N^+I_3 , $ClCH_2COONa$, NH_2NH_2 , (ii) $RCHO$.

Synthesis of some New Thiosemicarbazides and Thiosemicarbazones as Possible Antitubercular and Antibacterial Agents

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THIOSEMICARBAZIDES and thiosemicarbazones are associated with broad spectrum biological activities¹. The present work is undertaken with a view to synthesise compounds having better biological properties. Some dithiosemicarbazones were synthesised by reaction of 4,4'-diaminobiphenylmethane (1) with 4,4'-diaminobiphenyl ether (4) via dithiosemicarbazides with aromatic aldehydes (Schemes 1 and 2). The structures of the

Scheme 1. Reagents: (i) CS_2 , liq. NH_3 , $ClCH_2COONa$, NH_2NH_2 , (ii) $RCHO$.

Experimental

M.p.s are uncorrected. Microanalysis was performed on a Coleman instrument. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Shimadzu 408 spectrophotometer and pmr spectra on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 (90 MHz) spectrometer using TMS as an internal standard.

4,4'-Di(3-thiosemicarbazide)biphenylmethane (2): A mixture of 4,4'-diaminobiphenylmethane (0.01 mol), ethanol (30 ml) and NH_4OH (20 ml) was cooled below 30° and carbon disulphide (8 ml) added slowly during 15 min with shaking and then allowed to stand for 1 h. Sodium monochloroacetate (0.02 mol) was added to it followed by the addition of 50% hydrazine hydrate (14 ml). The reaction mixture was concentrated to half of its volume and allowed to stand overnight. The resulting thiosemicarbazide was crystallised from DMF, (69%), m.p. 194° (Found: C, 52.50; H, 5.51; N, 24.03. $C_{14}H_{14}N_6S_2$ requires: C, 52.02; H, 5.20; N, 24.27%); ν_{max} (KBr) 3360–3330 ($N-H$) and 1110 cm^{-1} ($C=S$); δ (DMSO) 3.9 (2H, s, CH_2), 7.1–7.6 (8H, m, Ar), 9.65 (4H, br, NH); m/z 314 ($M^+ - N_2H_4$), 282 ($M^+ - 2N_2H_4$), 272 ($M^+ - C(=S) - NHNH_2$) and 240 ($272 - N_2H_4$).

4,4'-Di(3-thiosemicarbazide)biphenyl ether (5): It was synthesised by following the method described above, and the product crystallised from DMF-water, (71%), m.p. $197-98^\circ$ (Found: C, 48.76; H, 4.71; N, 23.66. $C_{14}H_{14}N_6S_2O$ requires: C, 48.27; H, 4.59; N, 24.10%); ν_{max} (KBr) 3300–3200 ($N-H$) and 1190 cm^{-1} ($C=S$); δ (DMSO) 7.10–7.85 (8H, m, Ar), 9.25 (4H, br, NH); m/z 316 ($M^+ - N_2H_4$), 284 ($M^+ - 2N_2H_4$), 274 ($M^+ - C(=S) - NHNH_2$) and 242 ($274 - N_2H_4$).

4,4'-Di(substituted-benzaldehyde-3-thiosemicarbazide)biphenylmethane (3): A mixture of 2 (0.01 mol) and aromatic aldehyde (0.02 mol) was refluxed in ethanol (95%; 50 ml) for 2 h. The reaction